

Gomutra Haritaki: An Emerging Ayurvedic Medicine

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Abstract:- Gomutra Haritaki is an Ayurvedic medication listed in Samhitas such as Charaka samhita, Sushrutasmhita, Ashtanga hridayam, and others. Shoth (oedema), Arsha (haemorrhoids), and Pandu are some of the disorders for which this medicine has been prescribed (Anaemia). There are several references on the qualities of Gomutra (Cow's Urine) and Haritaki(Terminalia Chebula Fruit) in various Samhitas. The many ways for preparing Gomutra Haritaki are outlined. This is a multifaceted medicine that may be used to treat a variety of ailments. An attempt was made to assemble all of the details of GomutraHaritaki from classics, as well as its preparation process.

Keywords:- Gomutra, Haritaki, Boiling, Roasting, piles, health benefits.

I. INTRODUCTION

As a comprehensive therapeutic system, Ayurveda has expanded and developed. It offers a comprehensive understanding of natural therapies (from plants, animals, and minerals) that have long been utilised to maintain health and reduce the harmful consequences of bodily illnesses. Despite being a medical discipline, Ayurveda also offers thorough explanations of other medical professions, such as pharmaceutical science. Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals is scientific and based on millennia of experience. Many elements of Ayurvedic pharmaceuticals, such as the collection of raw materials from natural sources, their identification and validation, various purification, manufacturing, and analytical procedures, medicine shelf life and storage techniques, and so on, have a huge quantity of literature. All of these important themes have been presented in a scientific manner, but in order for current pharmaceuticals advances to be acknowledged worldwide, they must be integrated into existing research. Gomutra haritaki is a drug that comprises the biochemical components Gomutra (Animal product) and Haritaki (Plant product), both of which are used to treat a number of ailments. In Ayurvedic scriptures, Gomutra haritaki is used to treat Pandu roga (Anemia), Mukharoga

(Mouth problems), and Arsha roga (Mouth infections) (Piles) [1].

Gomutra and Haritaki are widely used in Ayurveda. Both drugs are Ushna (Hot) in character and can aid in the treatment of Vata (one of the body's humours) and Kapha ailments. Arsha, Pandu, Shoth, and Mukhroga are all treated with Gomutra Haritaki, a pharmaceutical produced from Gomutra and Haritaki (Disorders of Oral Cavity). Gomutra Haritaki comes in a number of forms, including Gomutra Bhavit (Triturated), Gomutra Klinna (Impregnated), and Gomutra Pakva (Boiled). Each of these approaches has its own set of benefits and drawbacks [2].

II. GOMUTRA HARITAKI HEALTH BENEFITS

Gomutra Haritaki is a popular weight-loss and mouth-disease remedy. Eczema, dermatitis, and other skin diseases have been treated with the same. The wonderful effects of GomutraHaritaki include itching associated with Renal Insufficiency, Tumours - Benign and Malignant, Obesity, High Cholesterol, Anaemia, Gout, Constipation, High BP, Nephrotic Syndrome, Chronic Renal Failure, Polycystic Kidneys, Systemic Lupus Erythematosus, Dyslipidaemia, Sickle Cell Anaemia, Benign Prostatic Hypertrophy It also helps to mitigate the negative effects of food poisoning, chemical fertilisers, and pesticides. It can also be used as a dietary supplement by healthy people to avoid health issues caused by poor eating habits and a sedentary lifestyle.

III. USES OF GOMUTRA HARITAKI

- Oral cavity/mouth illness diseases
- Gout, rheumatism, and other rheumatic diseases
- Constipation, digestive weakness, and delayed intestinal movement are all symptoms of digestive weakness.
- It facilitates bowel evacuation.
- Piles or Arsha (Haemorrhoids)
- Pandu (Anemia)
- Shoth (Oedema) (figure 1)

Fig. 1: Pictorial representation of health benefits of Gomutra Haritaki.

IV. PREPARATION METHODS FOR GOMUTRA HARITAKI

Gomutra Haritaki is an Ayurvedic medication listed in Samhitas such as Charaka samhita, Sushruta samhita, Ashtangahridayam, and others. Shoth (oedema), Arsha (haemorrhoids), and Pandu are some of the disorders for which this medicine has been prescribed (Anemia). In many Samhitas, allusions to the qualities of Gomutra (Cow's Urine) and Haritaki (Fruit of Terminalia Chebula) can be found. The many ways for preparing Gomutra Haritaki are outlined. This is a multifaceted medicine that may be used to treat a variety of ailments. An attempt was made to assemble all of the details of Gomutra Haritaki from the classics, as well as its preparation procedure.

Ayurveda makes extensive usage of Gomutra and Haritaki. Both medications are Ushna (Hot) in nature and can help with Vata (one of the body's humours) and Kapha illnesses. Arsha, Pandu, Shoth, and Mukhroga have all been treated with Gomutra Haritaki, a medication made from Gomutra and Haritaki (Disorders of Oral Cavity). Gomutra Haritaki can be made in a variety of ways, including Gomutra Bhavit (Triturated), Gomutra Klinna (Impregnated), and Gomutra Pakva (Boiled). Each of these strategies has its own set of advantages and disadvantages. This page examines the numerous techniques of preparing this medicine, as well as the opinions of various writers and commenters, in order to provide a thorough knowledge.

Gomutra Haritaki references from ancient Ayurvedic writings such as Charakasamhita, Sushrutsamhita, and Ashtang Hridayam, among others, have been gathered. The

many techniques of preparing the same medication are examined critically [3,4,5,6].

A. Sushruta Samhita

In Shushka Arsha Chikitsa (Piles), Gomutra siddha Haritaki is prescribed to improve Agni's state and to calm Arsha's signs and symptoms. It should be taken in Pragbhakta kaal (Prior to eating) and with honey. According to Dalhana, this formulation is for those who have a clogged bowel habit and a low Agni (digestive fire) level (GadhvitkasyaMandagni:). Because of the dryness of this formula, it is also recommended that abstinence be observed during therapy [3].

B. Charaka Samhita

Haritaki combined with cow's urine is used to treat oedema of the Kaphaja kind. Haritaki soaked overnight in Gomutra should be administered to Piles sufferers. It's best if it's served with jaggery. Patients with Pandu roga of the Kaphaja kind should take Haritaki impregnated with Cow's Urine [4].

C. Ashtanga Hridayam

Two hundred Haritaki are boiled in one drone of cow' pee till the urine evaporates. Haritaki combined with honey, taken twice a day, heals piles, leprosy, dropsy, abdominal tumours, malignant tumours, goitre, obesity, anaemia, and thigh stiffness caused by Kapha. In the treatment of Kaphaja Arsha, Gomutra pakva Haritaki is recommended. Gomutra Haritaki should be administered to people suffering from Shoth (Oedema) for Shodhan purposes. Haritaki is cooked in cow's urine till it loses its form (becomes minced), then the powders of Jala, Mishi, and Kushtha are macerated in this

thick liquid. As the monarch was not plagued by worthless men, the individual who drinks even a particle of this medicine would not be troubled by oral diseases [5].

D. Brihat Nighantu Rantakar

In Pandu Roga, Gomutra Haritaki is mentioned. Haritaki should be administered the Gomutra bhavana for three weeks, according to legend. Then it should be taken once a day in a dose of one Haritaki [6].

E. Vangasena

A week after taking Haritaki cooked in castor oil made from cow's urine, one gets free of Shleepad (Filariasis) [7].

In cases where shodhan (purification) is required, Gomutra Haritaki is employed. Following alternative ways is suggested after reading numerous sources.

- Haritaki with cow's urine trituration
- Haritaki steeped in cow's urine overnight
- Boil Haritaki in a Cow's Urine.
- Haritaki is taken with the urine of a cow.
- Haritaki is cooked in Castor oil and then eaten with cow's.

Research was carried out on the microbial contamination of several Gomutra-containing formulations. Microbial contamination was investigated in three Ayurvedic formulations: Punarnava Mandura, Sanjeevani Vati, and Gomutra Haritaki. According to the findings, Gomutra Haritaki had the highest fungal growth and overall viable aerobic bacterial count. 11 According to all of these publications, Haritaki can demonstrate fungal growth or enhanced aerobic bacterial contamination when soaked in cow's pee or triturated in cow's urine. Whereas, according to Ashtangahridayam, Haritaki should be cooked in cow's urine to ensure that it is contamination free [8].

V. GOMUTRA HARITAKI'S THERAPEUTIC PROPERTIES

A. In obesity

Obesity is becoming more prevalent among India's middle-class population. Many Indians have begun to rely on processed meals, which include high levels of trans-fat, carbohydrates, and other hazardous and artificial substances. Obesity is thought to be at the root of many ailments. Increased weight has been linked to an increased risk of cancer, diabetes, heart disease, and stroke. Junk food, alcohol, and a sedentary lifestyle are causing quiet self-destruction in India, with one out of every five men and women being fat or overweight. On 21 patients, an observational pilot research was undertaken on the effects of Gomutra Haritaki, food control, and exercise in the management of Sthaulya (obesity). Enrolled individuals were screened and divided into two groups based on clinical results. For eight weeks, the trial group was given Gomutra Haritaki (6 g/day in three separate doses), whereas the control group was given placebo capsules in the same dose. Weight loss (P 0.001) and body mass index (BMI) decrease (P 0.01) were shown to be statistically highly significant in both groups. In comparison to the experimental group, the control group performed better. These findings demonstrate

the role of nutrition and exercise in the treatment of Sthaulya [9].

B. In dyslipidemia

Dyslipidemia is a disease of lipoprotein metabolism that includes lipoprotein overproduction or deficiency. It is best characterised in Ayurvedic terms as Kapha MedoMargavarana (dyslipidemia), Atisthaulya (obesity), or MedaRoga and Prameha. Gomutra Haritaki (GH) is discussed in Charaka Samhita under Shotha Chikitsa and Ashtanga Hridaya under Arsha Chikitsa. AsanadiGhanavati (AG) is a modified presentation of AsanadiGanapati alluded to in Ashtanga Hridaya. Research was carried out in which patients with a high lipid profile were randomly divided into two groups. Patients in Group A (n = 30) received a tablet of AG 1 g (500 mg each) three times a day for eight weeks, whereas patients in Group B (n = 30) received a tablet of GH at a comparable dose and duration. Body circumference, BMI, cardinal symptoms such as Anga-Gaurava, Bharavridhi, and lipid profile characteristics were used to evaluate the therapy's effectiveness. AG reduced serum cholesterol by 7.12 percent, serum triglyceride (S. TG) by 7.72 percent, serum low density lipoprotein (S. LDL) by 11.68 percent, serum very low-density lipoprotein (S. VLDL) by 7.73 percent, and serum high density lipoprotein (S. HDL) by 9.52 percent, with moderate improvement in 14.81 percent and mild improvement in 70.37 percent of patients. The GH reduced blood cholesterol by 6.31 percent, serum TG by 9.61 percent, serum LDL by 12.55 percent, serum VLDL by 8.99 percent, and serum HDL by 10.52 percent, with considerable improvement in 3.70 percent of patients and mild improvement in 74.07 percent. As a result, AG and GH are recommended for usage in Kleda Bahul Samprapti Janya Vyadhi and Ama Bahul Samprapti Janya Vyadhi, respectively [10].

C. In Antiphospholipid antibody syndrome

The occurrence of thrombo-embolic problems and pregnancy morbidity in the context of consistently increasing titers of anti-phospholipid antibody (APLA) syndrome is known as anti-phospholipid antibody (APLA) syndrome. Its clinical manifestations can be varied, and any organ might be affected, making it a current concern in a wide range of surgical and medical specialities. The example of a 34-year-old young girl with APLA syndrome who developed cerebral venous thrombosis and then deep vein thrombosis of the left leg veins is given here. Three types of APLAs were found to be increased (IgG, IgM, and activated protein C). Other autoimmune or systemic disorders were not found in clinical or laboratory tests. The patient is receiving RukshaTikshnaVirechana (purgation) using Haritaki (Terminalia chebula Retz.) and Goarka (cow's urine extract) under the concept of KaphajaShotha (nonpitting edoema) and has shown considerable improvements in both subjective and objective indicators. Though APS is an autoimmune disease with few treatment choices, if it is treated appropriately according to Ayurveda's core principles and in the light of Shotha Chikitsa, good outcomes can be reached, giving hope for its future treatment without side effects [11].

D. Liver Cirrhosis with Ascites

Cirrhosis of the liver with ascites is a difficult medical condition. Cirrhosis of the liver is the last stage of many chronic liver disorders. It comprises two phases: compensatory and decompensatory. The compensated period might persist for years. Major consequences of decompensated cirrhosis include jaundice, variceal bleeding, ascites, and encephalopathy. The most prevalent symptom is ascites. In 10 years, 50% of compensated cirrhosis patients develop ascites. A case study with fantastic results in liver cirrhosis was published. The study included records with the Nitya virechana technique, a minimum of 7 days of hospitalisation, adequate paperwork, and satisfying the other inclusion and exclusion criteria. Abdominal girth measurements at the umbilicus, Xiphisternum to umbilicus measurement, Umbilicus to pubic symphysis measurement, weight, clinical global impression (CGI) scales (Severity, improvement, and efficacy index), haemoglobin, liver function tests, Prothrombin time, INR, and renal function tests were all used to evaluate the patients. The study's methodological requirements were satisfied by 55 case records. The patients had stage 3 decompensated cirrhosis and a Child-Turcotte-Pugh Score of class C. The results of 15 days of therapies were analysed. Baseline, 7th, 9th, 11th, and 15th day of therapy assessments were performed. Nitya virechana, oral medicaments, food, salt, and hydration limits were among the interventions. Ayurvedic therapies improved different abdomen measures, weight, CGI scales, haemoglobin, liver function tests, prothrombin ran time, INR, and renal function tests significantly ($p < 0.001$) at all time points. In patients with decompensated cirrhosis, complicated Ayurvedic therapies such as nityavirechana, oral drugs, diet, fluid and salt limits enhance the clinical profile, liver function, renal function, prothrombin time, and INR parameters, which justifies further research [12].

VI. CONCLUSION

Gomutra Haritaki is a medicine made up of the biological components Gomutra (Animal product) and Haritaki (Plant product), which are both used to cure a variety of diseases. The characteristics of Gomutra (Cow's Urine) and Haritaki (Terminalia Chebula Fruit) are mentioned in multiple Samhitas. There are several methods for making Gomutra Haritaki. This is a versatile drug that may be used to treat a wide range of diseases. Gomutra Haritaki prepared by triturating Haritaki with cow's pee or soaking Haritaki in cow's urine might be contaminated with a variety of germs and fungi. Obesity, hyperlipidemia, liver cirrhosis, piles, anaemia, and other disorders have all been treated with Gomutra Haritaki. In the following years, many health advantages linked with this excellent medicine will need to be investigated.

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